

EFFECT OF TRICHODERMA AND POTASSIUM HUMATE ON SYMBIOTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF SOYBEAN

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Abstract. The article studies the complex effect of the micromycete *Trichoderma asperellum*, potassium humate and rhizotorphin on the biological nitrogen-fixing capacity of soybean plants grown in the soil climate of the Kurdemir region of Azerbaijan. It is shown that all three preparations separately have a positive effect on the symbiotic system of the soybean plant, but their complex effect is more effective. This is clearly seen in the number of active nodules formed (leghemoglobin nodules), the height and weight of the plants.

Keywords: soybean, *Tr. asperellum*, potassium humate, *Rhizobium japonicum*, leghemoglobin, symbiosis.

Introduction. Environmental pressure on agrobiocenosis, growing demand for agricultural products of the world population make it necessary to use innovative technologies in Egyptian agriculture. One of the promising and modern methods of increasing the productivity and quality of plants is the optimization of nitrogen fixation using rhizobial bacteria, biological preparations and micromycetes in agrobiocenoses. For this purpose, various biological preparations and associations of microorganisms are widely used [1, 2].

Micromycetes *Trichoderma* are useful microorganisms that spread in the rhizosphere of plants and have a developed enzymatic system. They synthesize physiologically active substances that can affect biochemical processes in plants. They stimulate the protective properties of plants against harmful organisms. They are polyantagonists and stop the development of most pathogenic microorganisms that live in the rhizosphere of plants in a normal environment [3,4].

Potassium humate (K-humate) is a highly effective growth stimulator, easily absorbed by plant organs. In addition to the high content of microelements, it contains 5% humic acids, 10% potassium, 2.8% total nitrogen and 0.4% phosphorus. By improving plant nutrition, they accelerate their transition to phenological phases and activate biochemical processes [5].

Although there are separate studies on the influence of *Trichoderma* micromycete and K-humate on various morphological, physiological and biochemical effects in plants, there is no information on the complex use of these two factors. Therefore, the article studies the role of *Trichoderma* micromycete and K-humate in the formation of symbiotic properties of the soybean plant.

Material and methods. The experiments were carried out at the Karrar experimental station of the Institute of Botany of the Kurdamir region. Large agrochemical analyzes of the sown area were carried out: pH-7.9; EC25 -0.67 ms/cm; Carbonation (CaCO₃) -5.9%; Hummus 1.9%; Nitrogen (N) -0.062%; Phosphorus (P₂O₅) -28 ppm; Potassium (K) -143 ppm; Calcium (Ca) –

1250 ppm; Magnesium (Mg) -182 ppm; Sodium (Na) -249 ppm; Iron (Fe) – 5.6 ppm; Copper (Cu) -2.2 ppm; Zinc (Zn) -0.8 ppm; Manganese (Mn) -3.7 ppm; Boron (B) -0.075 ppm As you can see, the sown area is not as nutritious as it is energetically.

The soybean plant variety "Bravo" (*Glicina hispida* L.) was used in the studies. The seeds were superficially sterilized in 96% ethyl alcohol for 5 minutes, air-dried, and before planting, soaked in a culture solution of the micromycete *Trichoderma asperellum* for about 15 hours and in rhizodern (200 g of the preparation is intended for treating seeds planted per 1 ha) for 6 hours. In the first 3 phases of leaf formation, the above-ground part was sprayed with a 0.002% solution of potassium humate according to the experimental variants. The plants were grown until the beginning of the flowering phase and analyzed (49 days after sowing the seeds in the soil). Field experiments were carried out in 3 replicates. The efficiency of symbiotic nitrogen fixation was determined by the number and color of nitrogen-fixing rhizomes, as well as the height and weight of the plants [6].

Experimental part. The obtained results showed that *Tr. asperellum* and potassium humate had a positive effect on the formation of nodules in the plant roots, but the percentage of efficiency was different (Table 1). Compared with the control, the *Trichoderma*-treated plants showed a significant increase in the weight of one root tuber (37.2% compared to the control), if not more (2 units more), which was ultimately more clearly manifested in the nodules of 1 plant, compared with the control. Thus, compared with the control, the plant treated with *Tr. asperellum* had 46.5% more root nodules. One of the main indicators of the efficiency of symbiotic nitrogen fixation is the color of the resulting nodules. The fact that the nodules are pink indicates the formation of effective symbiosis. This depends on the presence of leghemoglobin in them. Leghemoglobin (Lb) is found only in active tuber bacteria. Lb is an oxygen-carrying hemoprotein of the roots of leguminous plants and, by providing oxygen for the process of nitrogen fixation, protects it from high concentrations, i.e. regulates the oxygen supply [7]. We noticed that 17 nodules treated with *Tr. asperellum* were pink. In the control plants it was 11.

Table 1. Effect of *Tr. asperellum* (*Tr.*) and potassium humate (*K-humate*) on the quantity, weight and amount of Lb-treated soybean nodules treated with rhizotorphin

Variants	Root nodules one plant (in quantity)	Weight of one nodules (mg)	Weight of nodules of one plant (mg)	Lb nodules one plant (quantity)
Control (C)	17±0,09	4,81±0.15	81.7±0.88	11±0,09
C+Tr	19±0.11	6.3±0.12	119.7±1,1	15±0,08
C+ K-hummat	27±0.10	9.8±0.19	264.6±1.12	23±0,11
C+Tr+K-hummat	31±0.46	14.7±1.01	455.7±1,87	27±0,10

Spraying the aboveground part of the plant with a 0.002% solution of potassium humate had a more effective effect on the establishment of effective symbiosis between rhizobial bacteria and soybeans than *Trichoderma*. Treatment with potassium humate additionally stimulated the formation of nitrogen-fixing nodules on the roots - 27 units / plant. This means 58.8% more than in the control, and 42.1% more than in *Trichoderma*. The color of the nodules was darker pink than in the other two variants, and the number of active nodules was 23.

The study of the number, weight and colour of nodules formed in the roots of the soybean plant showed that the *Tr. asperellum* + potassium humate variant was more effective in terms of tuber activity. The size of the nodules of this variant was larger than the others and their weight was high, the weight of nodules in the roots of one plant was 455.7 mg. The number of active nodules (nodules with Lb) was 27, and the colour became bright red, which is the highest indicator of symbiotic activity compared to the other three variants (Table 1).

We noticed that the use of *Tr. asperellum* and potassium humate affects the height and weight of soybean plants. Due to the effect of *Tr. asperellum*, the height of the plants was 3.2 cm higher than that of the control plants, and due to the effect of potassium humate - 8 cm (Figure 1). The combined effect of *Tr. asperellum* and potassium humate on the height of soybean plants was more effective, the height of the plants was 10.5 cm higher than the control plant.

Treatment of the plant with a culture solution of the micromycete *Trichoderma* and potassium humate also resulted in an increase in phytomass. However, the phytomass of the plant treated with *Trichoderma* and the control plant was the same (Fig. 2). The presence of potassium humate in the medium increased the plant mass by 24.3% compared to the control. In plants of the *Trichoderma* + potassium humate variant, this increase was 29.7%.

Determination of the quantity, weight, color, height of plants and phytomass of soybean nodules showed that the combined use of *Tr. asperellum* and potassium humate is more appropriate in the soil and climatic conditions of the Kurdamir region. Thus, the nodules of plants of this variant more densely cover the root system, are larger in size and light red in color.

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